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Corrosion resistance of titanium suboxide coatings for titanium protection in PEM water electrolyzers

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Abstract

Bipolar plates (BPP), porous transport layers (PTL) and their precious metal coatings make up for more than half of the materials costs of the state-of-the-art proton exchange membrane water electrolyzer (PEMWE) stacks. Corrosion protection is a relevant aspect of the technology since the latter is very sensitive to low level (ppm) of cationic pollution that can bring about rapid degradation of the catalyst activity and the polymer membrane stability [1]. Thus, there is an increasing research effort for replacing platinum group metal-based coatings by more cost-effective alternatives in order to improve the economic competitiveness of PEMWE while maintaining its long-term durability.

This contribution will report some of the recent advances on the French-Swiss project “PROTIS” dedicated to corrosion protection of anodic PTL and BPP by thin layers of titanium suboxides (TiO_x, oxygen-deficient conductive titanium oxides) prepared by physical vapor deposition.

It was recently demonstrated that PTL and BPP do not experience similar electrochemical conditions in PEMWE [2]. While the PTL/catalyst interface undergoes highly anodic polarization in an acidic environment promoting corrosion, the BPP baths in pure near-neutral water at much lower potentials. Based on these findings, the ex situ corrosion behavior of TiO_x films deposited on titanium plates as a function of electrochemical, potential and pH will be presented. OCP monitoring, chronoamperometry, impedance spectroscopy results combined with post-mortem electron microscopy imaging and interfacial contact resistance measurements will be analyzed to assess the corrosion resistance of the coatings under both BPP-like and PTL-like conditions. The durability of the coatings tested during more than hundred hours of exposure will also be tackled.

Introduction

Proton exchange membrane water electrolyzers (PEMWE) constitute one of the low-temperature technologies for producing green or decarbonized hydrogen as an energy carrier and feedstock for industry in order to limit global warming and increase Europe's energy independency [3-5]. A PEMWE electrochemically splits water and is made up of i) bipolar plates (hereafter denoted BPP) whose role is to transport the liquid water and evacuate the gases produced and connect the single cells in an electrolysis stack, ii) porous transport layers (PTL) that ensure the electrical connection between the BPP and the electrodes while allowing the liquid water and the gases to pass through, and iii) a catalyst coated membrane (CCM) consisting of a proton-conducting polymer electrolyte membrane on which the electrodes (catalysts) are deposited (Figure 1a).

Figure 1: (a) PEMWE working principle with MEM being or the electrolyte membrane, CL the the catalyst layers (electrodes), BPP the bipolar plates and PTL the porous transport layers. The catalyst-coated membrane (CCM) is the assembly of the MEM and the CL. (b) Capital expenditures breakdown in a PEMWE stack. Both sketches are adapted from [6] under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0).

In the anode compartment, the state-of-the-art material is titanium for withstanding the harsh operating conditions, namely the acidic PTL/catalyst/electrolyte interphase and the elevated electrochemical potential (around + 1.6V/SHE) [1]. Furthermore, it is known that the native titanium oxide layer (that provides the resistance to corrosion) can be destabilized under oxidizing conditions (in PEMWE [7] as well as in other industrial applications, such as biomedical implants [8-9]). A resistive oxide layer tends to grow at the titanium surface, increasing the interfacial contact resistance (ICR) between adjoining elements and decreasing the electrolysis efficiency [7,10]. In order to address this issue, noble metal coatings (Au, Pt, Ir) have been utilized against BPP and PTL corrosion [11,12]. Nevertheless, in some cases, those protective coatings may peel off their substrates after several hundreds of hours of operation, resulting in the undesired pollution of the CCM and oxidation of the underlying titanium [10,12]. Furthermore, the main issue arising from the utilization of titanium structural elements coated with precious metal layers is that it negatively affects the capital expenditures (capex) of the technology. It is estimated that the BPP and PTL account for more than 60% of the capex of the PEM electrolyzer stacks, [6,13], as illustrated in Figure 1b. One way to reduce capex is to develop non-precious metal coatings, as presented in this work with sputtered titanium suboxide (TiOx) thin films.

1. Experimental

Thin (150 nm) TiO_x coatings were deposited using reactive magnetron sputtering from a titanium target at 75 W DC on commercially-pure titanium substrates. The coatings exhibited a dark blue / purple colour in as-deposited state. The chamber pressure was maintained at 3 mTorr while introducing Ar at 45 sccm and O₂ at 0.5 sccm. The substrate temperature was kept at 400 °C during deposition. To improve coating adhesion, a thin titanium interlayer was deposited prior to TiO_x. For comparison, uncoated titanium substrates were also used. The (coated and uncoated) substrates were cleaned with acetone but did not undergo any polishing process.

Ex situ corrosion testing was conducted using three-electrode double-jacketed cells connected to a thermoregulated circulation bath set at 60°C and a Gamry Interface 1010 potentiostat. The reference electrode was a reversible hydrogen electrode (RHE, from Gaskatel) and the counter-electrode was a platinum-coated titanium wire.

Taking into account the findings of Becker et al. on ionic decoupling [2], investigations under BPP-like conditions were done at open circuit potential (OCP) at near-neutral pH (around 5.5). This corresponds to a BPP adjoining a relatively thick PTL with no galvanic coupling between the two elements. For ex situ mimicking of the PTL/anode interface, a potential of +1.6 V/RHE was selected and the solution was sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄, pH = 1).

The surface state and the adhesion of the coated and uncoated samples were examined using naked eye, optical microscopy and scanning electron microscopy in pristine and post-mortem state. Interfacial contact resistance measurements (ICR) were performed at a pressure of ca. 1.5 MPa using a gold-coated copped cube as contact element.

2. Results

The baseline PTL-related experiment was carried out with uncoated titanium. After 72 hours of anodic polarization at +1.6V/RHE, the titanium surface exhibited a clear degradation (Figure 2). The decrease of current density is associated with the protective effect of the titanium oxide layer that grows on the surface, probably following a dissolution-redeposition process at the vicinity of the substrate surface, yielding a typical yellowish discoloration and exhibiting a partially porous microstructure. It can be hypothesized that this dissolution-redeposition mechanism would release some titanium in the electrolyte which could generate a catalyst or membrane pollution in the PEMWE environment. The formation of the oxide layer brings about an increase of the ICR from ca. 1 mΩ cm² to 2-3 mΩ cm² the relatively short duration of the experiment (72 hours, while durability measurements usually exceed several hundred hours).

Figure 2: Corrosion of uncoated titanium under PTL-like conditions for 72 hours (H_2SO_4 , pH = 1, +1.6V/RHE, 60°C) (a) chronoamperometry curve; (b) photograph of the sample after anodic polarization showing exposed and unexposed areas; (c) SEM micrograph of the exposed (corroded) area; (d) SEM micrograph of the unexposed area (~pristine state).

The same experimental conditions were used for the TiO_x-coated titanium, except that the duration was extended to 162 hours. The current density was much smaller ($< 0.1 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) than without coating ($0.1\text{-}10 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$, Figure 2a), suggesting that the coating hindered the corrosion of the underlying substrate (Figure 3). The post-mortem SEM analysis of the TiO_x surface revealed no sign of damage (pitting or dissolution) and a good adhesion to the substrate. However the ICR, initially below $10 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ in as-deposited state, reached ca. $20 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ after the polarization experiment.

The TiO_x coatings were tested under BPP-like conditions at open-circuit potential in near-neutral solution for almost the same duration (164 hours). In that case, the stability of the coating was monitored by electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (as the current density was zero throughout the experiment). This was achievable solely by adding a supporting salt (namely Na_2SO_4) into the electrolyte to get a good conductivity (ca. $1 \text{ mS}/\text{cm}$). Unsurprisingly, in view of the results under harsher PTL-like conditions, the TiO_x survived the milder BPP-like testing conditions with a stable OCP of ca. 600-700 mV/RHE and a well-adherent coating. The impedance (Nyquist plots) exhibited little variation during the experiment as well (Figure 4). Yet, as in the case of PTL-related experiments (presented above), the ICR was above the $10 \text{ m}\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ target after the experiment. It must be noted that experiments in low conductivity solution (around $1 \mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), that did not enable to record impedance spectra (due to too high the resistance of the electrolyte), yielded the same coating adherence and open-circuit potential stability (not shown here).

Figure 3: Chonoamperometry curve of TiO_x-coated titanium under PTL-like conditions for 162 hours (H₂SO₄, pH = 1, +1.6V/RHE, 60°C) for 162 hours. Insert: photograph of the coating surface after the polarization.

Figure 4: Nyquist plots of TiO_x-coated titanium under BPP-like conditions for 164 hours (pH ~ 5.5, OCP, 60°C) in conductive Na₂SO₄ solution (1 mS/cm) for 162 hours. Insert: photograph of the coating surface after testing.

To summarize, thin TiO_x layers prepared by magnetron sputtering are potential candidates to replace noble coatings for anodic BPP and PTL made of titanium aiming at reducing capital expenditures. Further research is currently ongoing to limit or avoid the increase of interfacial contact resistance with time. The latter may be related to reoxidation of the surface that has to be fully characterized and quantified for both PTL- and BPP-like conditions as a function of time. Titanium suboxide might also be considered to protect stainless steel BPP and PTL (contribution A0217).

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